

Visual Method for Representing DNA and RNA

The widely accepted representation of DNA and RNA is based on the five letters U, C, A, G, T that stands for the five nucleic acids: Uracil, Cytosine, Adenine, Guanine and Thymine. The idea here is to introduce a set of five simple visual elements that can be used to represent these amino acids. We will begin with the black & white scale shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

This scale represents a continual and gradual transition from black to white. On this scale we will identify five distinct qualities and name them: Black (B), Dark Gray (D), Gray (G), Light Gray (L) and White (W). These five qualities we will visually define by the discrete five element scale shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

Expressed in percentages, these qualities are quantified (defined numerically) as values of "black" (or "white"): Black = 100% black (or 0% white), Dark Gray = 75% black (25% white), Gray = 50% black (or 50% white), Light Gray = 25% black (75% white), and White = 0% black (100% white). We may notice that all these qualities are defined through only one quality, and that is "black." This quality we will consider to be given and it will not be defined here. An opposite quality of "black" on the scale is "white." This quality is expressed here as the absence of "black" and thus its value is defined as 0% black. We will also define an operation "negative" (*) for the five elements on the discrete scale. This operation transforms one element on the scale into another element on the same scale in this way: $B^* = W$, $D^* = L$, $G^* = G$, $L^* = D$, and $W^* = B$. Visually it is defined as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3

The starting image we will call the "positive" image (Fig. 3a), while the result will be the "negative" image (Fig. 3b). Pairs Black - White, and Dark Gray - Light Gray will always be copied one into another, while Gray is copied only into itself (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4

The negative of Gray can only be Gray. In other words, Gray is neutral to the operation N. The value difference between these pairs is not the same. For B and W it is 100% black, for D and L it is 50% black and for G it is 0% black. On the other hand the sum of the values for each pair is the same and it is 100% black (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5

We will now propose a correspondence between these five discrete values and five nucleic acids in both DNA and RNA. In this visual presentation Black = Uracil, Dark Gray = Cytosine, Gray = Adenine, Light Gray = Guanine, and White = Thymine, as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6

Out of 120 possible combinations, it seems this is the only one (or its negative) that can be used to represent all five nucleic acids. There are well established relationships between nucleic acids for both DNA and RNA. These relationships are defined by the processes of replication within the DNA double helix, and transcription between DNA and RNA. For the DNA-DNA relationship, the base pairs are defined as T - A and C - G, while for the DNA-RNA the base pairs are defined as A - U and C - G. In the visual presentation these base pairs will be defined as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7

What is interesting about this presentation of the base pairs is that it corresponds visually to the actual relationships between the bases. Values that represent C and G (D and L) relate to each other as positive and negative. Also, value G (represents Adenine) is a blend of equal proportions of Black and White and thus placed in the middle between Black and White. Similarly Adenine is placed in the middle between Thymine (White) and Uracil (Black). We may also notice that the value difference between the base pairs is the same for all pairs and is equal to 50% black. This constant value corresponds to the value representation for Adenine. On the other hand the value difference between the neighboring bases is by definition 25% black (Fig. 6). If this value is defined as one step, then to move from one base to its corresponding pair we will need two steps ($25\% + 25\% = 50\%$). In other words, two neighboring qualities (bases) could not form a base pair. For example, if we add 50% black to T we will arrive at A. And this is the only option available to T. If we add the same value to G we will arrive at C. Now, at C we cannot add 50% black, but by subtracting this amount we will get back at G. From U we also have only one option, by subtracting 50% black we will get at A. However, if we are at A we will have two options. By adding 50% black we will arrive at U, and by subtracting the same amount we will get back to T. The position of Adenine (Gray), in this representation is the only one that has two options, one toward Uracil (Black) and another toward Thymine (White).

DNA replication and RNA transcription can be seen also as an operations that transform an image that is "original" into another image that is its "copy." Unlike in the operation "negative," there is no "neutral" element here. In fact, the previously neutral element (Gray) here becomes an "ambivalent" element (Gray - A) that can be transformed (copied) into two opposite elements: Black (U) and White (T). On the other hand the base pair C-G behaves identically here as in the operation "negative." As it is shown previously a set of five values defined by the discrete scale (Fig. 6) represents five nucleic acids of both DNA and RNA. A subset of four values shown in Fig. 8a represents only those that are participating in DNA, while another subset of four (Fig. 8b) belongs to RNA.

Fig. 8

The visual representation of the base pairs for both DNA replication and RNA transcription is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9

A triplet of nucleotides that code for a single amino acid is called codon. There are 64 codons that define the entire genetic code. A visual representation of the genetic code for DNA and RNA in separate blocks (cycluses) of four codons is shown in Fig. 10, and in the integral form in Fig. 11.

Fig. 10

Fig. 11

We may notice that the RNA representation is darker (25% black) than the DNA representation. By comparing the transitions from dark to light that are taking place here (Fig. 11) in three different frequencies (16, 4, 1) for all three bases respectively, we will see that there exists a "dark shift" between

DNA and RNA. It is illustrated here only for the third base (Fig. 12), as if RNA is "lagging" one step behind the DNA.

Fig. 12

Let us now define a qualitative structure of $n+1$ elements (qualities) Q_{n+1} , where all elements have two neighbors except two (q_1 and q_{n+1}), which have only one neighbor: $Q_{n+1} = q_1 \wedge q_2 \wedge q_3 \wedge \dots \wedge q_{n+1}$. This is a linear qualitative structure with two end elements (limits). In the case of a visual presentation of the five nucleotides the qualitative structure is $Q_5 = B \wedge D \wedge G \wedge L \wedge W$. Here qualities D, G and L have two neighbors while B and W have only one. We will also define a substructure Q_n that has one element less than Q_{n+1} , but has same properties: $Q_n = q_1 \wedge q_2 \wedge q_3 \wedge \dots \wedge q_n$. In our case these are four nucleotides that define DNA or RNA:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DNA} &\Rightarrow Q_d = D \wedge G \wedge L \wedge W, \text{ or } Q_d = C \wedge A \wedge G \wedge T \\ \text{RNA} &\Rightarrow Q_r = B \wedge D \wedge G \wedge L, \text{ or } Q_r = U \wedge C \wedge A \wedge G \end{aligned}$$

In addition to these qualitative structures we will define a linear spatial structure of $n - 1$ elements (positions) where all elements have two neighbors except two (s_1 and s_{n-1}) which have one neighbor $S_{n-1} = s_1 \wedge s_2 \wedge s_3 \wedge \dots \wedge s_{n-1}$ (Fig. 13a). The special case represents structure where there are only two elements, each have one neighbor and there is no element with two neighbors (Fig. 13b).

Fig. 13

Another interesting case is a structure that has three elements (Fig. 13c). Here we have only one element (s_2) with two neighbors. This structure represents a basis for the definition of a codon. If we have a qualitative structure Q_n and spatial structure S_{n-1} , we could establish a correspondence between the elements of these two structures where the qualities occupy certain positions. We will name this correspondence a "state of space" or simply a "state." There are numerous states that can be defined with these two structures. We will here examine a special case of a state where the spatial neighborhood relationships coincide with qualitative neighborhoods. We can generate this state by placing quality q_1 in the position s_1 , quality q_2 in s_2 , q_3 in s_3 , until all positions ($n-1$) are occupied. We will name this state "Line 1" (L1). Since the last element (q_n) of the qualitative structure Q_n remains without a position, we will open another line (L2) by placing the quality q_n in the position s_1 . Then q_1 will be in s_2 , q_2 in s_3 and at the end of this line q_{n-2} will be placed in the position s_{n-1} . Now the quality q_{n-1} remains without a position and again we will start a new (third) line L3 and place q_{n-1} in s_1 , then q_n will be in s_2 , and so on until at the end of this line we place q_{n-3} in the position s_{n-1} . We can continue this procedure until all the qualities occupy all the positions only once at the time. In the line L_{n-1} we will have q_3 in the position s_1 and q_1 in s_{n-1} , while q_2 will be without a position. Finally, in the line L_n we will place q_2 in the position s_1 and on the other end q_n in the s_{n-1} . The quality q_1 will for the first time remain without its

position. The number of lines we need to place all the qualities of the Q_n in each position of S_{n-1} , one at the time, we will call a cycle. Here the cycle is n , since we need n lines to exhaust all the possibilities. If we now place all the lines one beneath the other respectively, we will get a visual structure that is $n-1$ positions wide and n positions high ($n-1 \times n$) where each of n qualities can occupy any of this positions (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14

This visual structure, defined by one cycle, we will call an "icon." In our case of DNA and RNA, each has four qualities that are placed in three positions. Thus the cycle here is $n = 4$ and the icon will be defined as 3×4 positions and four qualities. The icon defined with 3×4 positions and qualities D, G, L, and W, will be a DNA icon or "Dicon" (Fig. 15a), while for the qualities B, D, G, and L, it will be a RNA icon or "Ricon" (Fig. 15b).

Fig. 15

This Ricon (15b) is a transcription copy of Dicon 15a. Some examples of both Dicons and Ricons are shown in Fig. 16.

Fig. 16

Finally it might be interesting to see how four operations of copying defined above (neutral, negative, replication and transcription) can be applied on some of the characteristic Dicons (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17

Fig. 18

We assume here that there are 12x Q4d qualitative structures available in order to generate states with multiple positions occupied with the same quality.

Fig. 19

The icon can be a part of a larger spatial structure we could term a "genetic image" (Fig. 18) or it can be seen as a single frame of a time structure (process) that we could term a "genetic film" (Fig. 19).

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